

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES AS A FACTOR OF HUMAN DEVELOPMENT

Mishuk S.

*Belarusian Scientific Research Institute of Documentation
and Archival affairs*

*Ph.D. in Philosophy, Associate Professor, Deputy Director for Research
Minsk*

ABSTRACT

The article considers the role of info-communication technologies as a system-forming factor that determines the directions of social development of the information society. The article reveals their role in the transformation of human lifestyle and identifies the prospects of this process. The phenomenon of freelancing as a trend in the functioning of the labour force is analysed separately. Conclusions are drawn about the role of the system of info-communication technologies in the formation of both new requirements to production processes and the prerequisites for their implementation.

Keywords: civilization, information society, infocommunication technologies, digital economy, human beings, social relations, freelancing, intellectual migration.

The spread of information and communication technologies as a paradigmatic factor affecting society as a whole inevitably transforms its social sphere, its structure and dynamics of functioning and development.

The most visible, empirically recorded result of this impact is a jump-like increase in the number of people whose lives are directly related to the functioning of information and communication technologies. In our view, two main directions of social transformation should be emphasised.

First, the number of people who use information and communication technologies in their daily lives as consumers has increased dramatically.

Secondly, there has been a qualitative growth in the number of people directly employed in the sphere of information and communication technologies themselves. This social stratum became at the beginning of the XXI century obviously visible, very recognisable in the general social structure of society. (This process is in many respects similar to the phenomenon of the emergence of scientific and technical intelligentsia in the early 19th century during the Enlightenment.)

Several signs of such "recognisability and visibility" need to be recorded here.

First of all, the number of people employed in this sphere has sharply increased. If in the 80s representatives of this stratum were a certain "phenomenon", extremely rare in the sphere of intellectual labour, then 30-35 years later they are already very noticeable.

In addition, the level of their labour remuneration has fundamentally increased. Therefore, the prestige of workers in this sphere has grown qualitatively, and these professions have become very attractive.

And finally, with the development of the sphere of information and communication technologies and its penetration into almost all spheres of society, the social status (in the broad sense of the word) of workers involved in this sphere has also increased. They have be-

come a "respected" social stratum, whose opinion is listened to due to the understanding of their real importance for society.

The fixation of essential parallels in the history of the formation of this social stratum with the process of emergence of scientific and technical intelligentsia in the early 19th century seems to us quite reasonable. This process has, obviously, international character and has identical essential characteristics even in the states that differ significantly in the levels of socio-economic development.

Transformation of the social structure of modern society under the influence of information and communication technologies occurred simultaneously with the development of relevant socio-dynamic processes, with a sharp increase in the level of social mobility and the emergence of new forms of social mobility. One of them is intellectual migration, which has replaced the so-called "brain drain" process and has fundamentally surpassed it in terms of scale. (For example, about 1.8 million specialists leave Great Britain every year, about 800 thousand from Germany, and more than 200 thousand from Russia.)

Information and communication technologies create a new technical environment that objectively allows the process of intellectual migration to develop as truly international in its scale. A worldwide system of communications is emerging, which ensures the receipt, transmission, storage, exchange and use of information, functioning on the basis of unified components. This system is created on the basis of a common element and hardware base, with the use of common approaches to the architecture of network construction, with the use of common programming languages. This system uses unified technologies and procedures of information processing, unified norms and standards of service. An extremely important factor in the effective functioning of the information and communication technology system is the accessibility (cost and educational) of using the opportunities it provides. (The cost of an "average" level PC has been at the level of 1 thousand US dollars

for decades. To obtain basic knowledge of programming languages now does not require long training. For example, in India a programmer's diploma is obtained after 3-4 month courses).

Information and communications technology has become a highly visible sector of the global economy, with growth rates consistently outpacing those of the economy as a whole. Such rapid development of the information and communication technology sector is, in our opinion, due to the fact that it is structured as a sphere of almost "pure" labour, where the work of the employees involved plays a predominant role, and the role of technical equipment (in value terms) is incomparably small compared to the first component. Consequently, to create a new enterprise in this component of the economic system requires funds ten times less than in other components. Accordingly, the return on investment is many times higher. Therefore, the sphere of information and communication technologies has a particularly great need for highly qualified employees with a high level of education, who are able to quickly learn new forms and methods of work and are ready to quickly change jobs when the need arises. In other words, this area of the economy objectively requires an increase in the scale of intellectual migration and the transformation of this process into a truly global one.

The sector of information and communication technologies in the process of functioning forms "human material" corresponding to its needs. As mentioned above, a rather significant social stratum emerges, possessing common features regardless of the country of residence, cultural, national, family and etc. traditions.

The famous American futurologist E. Toffler in his book "The Third Wave" (1980) described the future society expected by 2025, where a person can work at home without leaving his home [1, p.246 - 248]. However, already ten years earlier information and communication technologies made it possible to work independently of the place of residence. A truly integrated and international labour market was formed, not bound by state borders, language barriers, time zones. A person could work in several companies simultaneously, and it depended only on his professional and personal qualities. In addition, there was a certain levelling of salaries in the field of information and communication technologies in the world as a whole. This has occurred both as a result of labour mobility and the constant demand for the most qualified employees by companies.

The ICT industry uses a relatively small number of "languages", allowing for easy interaction in the workplace. The availability of global means of information exchange effectively removes spatial and temporal constraints on the work process itself. The space of real "industrial communication" is significantly reduced and replaced by virtual communication. As a result, employees of the sphere of information and communication technologies turn out to be one of the most dynamic social stratum in its essence, experiencing no special difficulties even in case of real change of the place of work, which explains their significant involvement in the processes of intellectual migration, both real and virtual.

This social stratum has a similar nature of labour activity. Its representatives participate in the production of such a product, which, being abstract and universal in form, has the possibility, precisely because of these properties, to be used in a very large number of specific processes of production, management and consumption. The results of the work of representatives of this social stratum, being sufficiently massive, can be used quite quickly and without territorial, political, technological and other restrictions within the entire human civilisation. In addition, an information and communication technology as a way of exchanging the results of labour of this social stratum qualitatively reduces the terms of their distribution and direct use. As a result, a truly international (in the sense of not limited by borders) sphere is formed quite quickly, in which the existing national, technological, educational and other differences are levelled quite quickly. In its turn, the problem of preservation of the obtained results and, accordingly, the creation of rigid insurmountable frameworks for information exchange arises.

Representatives of the information and communication technologies sector in general have a fairly high (taking into account its number and national composition) educational level compared to the rest of the population. However, it should be taken into account that in recent years there has been a tendency of sharp increase in specialisation and narrowing of the scope of professional activity in this sphere. As a result, when solving a number of narrow tasks, it is not always necessary to have a high level of education and it is not necessary to spend a lot of time to train a specialist.

Information and communication technology workers are characterised by common ways and forms of labour activity. They are not rigidly bound to the place of residence, to the place of work, even to the time of direct labour activity. They can work at home at a convenient time without prejudice to the result of labour. As a result, freelancing is widespread as a form of labour convenient for both employer and employee. The employer does not need to create jobs in the traditional sense of the word, and the employee, accordingly, does not need one. In turn, the possibility of such a free "flow" of workers from one employer to another creates a serious problem of preserving the results obtained by the worker and preventing him/her from working for a competitor. (One of the classic forms of solving this problem is the system used in Microsoft Corporation of paying a certain percentage of a very high salary not in money, but in shares of the company).

Information and communication technologies also form a special environment for their employees, which were greatly facilitated by the development of the sphere of non-cash settlements. As a result, in modern conditions a person can perform work, receiving a task virtually and reporting on the results in the same way. He can receive his salary on a card account, which allows him to pay for virtual ordering and home delivery of food. In case of illness, a person is able to find information about medicines on the Internet and order them there. Education (and a diploma) can be obtained remotely. Leisure time is provided by interactive games. Communication with other people, family relations can

be transferred to the virtual format. In fact, an individual can live in a parallel world for quite a long time (it is not possible to determine the terms yet), and even in more than one world. In fact, we can say that the ideas of science-fiction writers are being realised - a person passes into another reality, and being in it, can pass from one reality to another, live several "virtual" lives at the same time. And many people are quite happy with this. (In Japan, this phenomenon has become so widespread that it has already been recorded by sociologists as a special trend and given its name - "otaku". Young men of 25-35 years old consciously do not want to live a real life, to meet really with representatives of the opposite sex, to really communicate, and spend all their time in virtual communication with their own kind). For many, their second, virtual identity actually turns out to be more important than their real one. (For example, there is a real problem of preserving the entire virtual life lived, and the loss of part of it is perceived as a real tragedy). Such a lifestyle, detaching people from reality, forms new value ideals and norms of their existence, an example of which is the intensive spread of "child-free" social culture, which was also foreseen by Toffler [1, p. 229 - 232].

Accordingly, it is possible to monitor the processes of existence of "personalities" in such an environment only by the results of their work, on the one hand, and by the movement of funds on personal card accounts, on the other. It is no longer possible to determine exactly how many real individuals are involved in this sphere, and how many of them are "purely virtual". As a result, as noted by the famous sociologist Sherry Turkle in her book "Collaborative Loneliness", these technologies, quantitatively expanding the possibilities of interaction between people, may eventually take away from them real human communication. [2, c. 144 - 185].

Based on the above, we can conclude that info-communication technologies, firstly, forming a global system of technical means of communication (technical devices, affordable and convenient to use even with a low level of education, appropriate technologies, norms

and rules of work) create preconditions and conditions for the emergence of a new type of social mobility - intellectual migration. This provides unprecedented opportunities for global human development.

Secondly, the ICT sphere provides the ever-increasing social demand for employees with high characteristics of social mobility, capable of rapid real change of place of work.

Thirdly, in the process of its functioning, the system of information and communication technologies itself forms a person with the corresponding characteristics: accustomed to work in similar conditions and at a similar rhythm, realistically and virtually moving depending on the needs of virtual production.

Fourthly, info-communication technologies as a component of the world economic system have an objective need for an appropriate infrastructure, which is created through, first of all, a qualitative increase in the sphere of non-cash financial settlements.

Thus, the sector of information and communication technologies, included in all components of human civilisation, integrates it as a single mechanism developing according to common, practically independent of the region laws. Moreover, it is truly international in its essential characteristics.

The formation of such a global "organism" would be impossible without the necessary number of people involved in this process. Since people are the most valuable component of the information and communication complex, not only developed but also developing countries were involved in the process of training the necessary personnel quite quickly. And here the process of globalisation and internationalisation of the world economic system was particularly pronounced.

References

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